

**Learning
Technology
Accelerator**

LEARNING TECHNOLOGY ACCELERATOR LEA

**D6.5 Report on dissemination activities M12
28.02.2019**

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1. Introduction

The LEA project started on 01 March 2018 with a kick-off meeting in Brussels (BE) in mid-March. Since then, the consortium has met in Halmstad (SE), Braga (PT), and London (UK). At these meetings, project developments and further steps were discussed, as well as dissemination opportunities. Some meetings also provided dissemination opportunities – especially Braga (local newspaper reports) and London (disseminating at the BETT show).

The project partners have continuously engaged in project dissemination work during this first phase of the LEA project in order to spread the word about the work LEA is doing. Over the remaining project period, the consortium members will continue to engage in dissemination activities, or even intensify their work in this respect. This document reports the dissemination activities from year 1 of LEA project. The dissemination approach has been described in D6.3 *LEA Awareness rising strategy and campaign*.

In order for all partners to have an overview of what is required from them in terms of dissemination, and in order to be able to track the partners' dissemination work, a Google document was created (see Figure 1). The colour coding in the Google document shows for which dissemination tasks the LEA partners have reached their targets (green), which they have started but not yet finished (yellow), and which they have not yet started (red). This document serves as a common space for partners to share their status in regards to project dissemination. All partners are asked to contribute to this document and note all the dissemination work they are doing for LEA. Via this document, all partners can share where they are in terms of project dissemination goals. It can be said that good progress is made and that partners are committed to fulfilling the application's dissemination objectives. The document contains the project's main dissemination goals and displays the tasks each partner has to fulfil in terms of general project dissemination. In addition to this, all partners are asked to complete further dissemination activities according to their possibilities and role in the project. As table 1 below shows, dissemination activities are being completed and partners are working towards reaching the goals assigned to them; the project consortium is making good progress with its dissemination activities.

It has to be noted that the Google document is a work in progress to which partners continuously contribute and that not all partners are able to update their completed tasks in the document immediately. Partners will, however, be reminded of their duty to update the document continuously.

	Actions & indicators of achievement	Numbers*
References	Project appears referenced on the partner's institutional website (university, faculty and/or research group)	14/16
LEA website	News stories provided (pictures, text etc.) for the LEA website. At least 3 per partner, e.g. event reporting, research report, stakeholders contacted	19/51
Social media followers	Get at least 60 followers per partner for LEA social media profiles: Facebook/Twitter/LinkedIn/Instagram /YouTube	504/1020
	Social media posts and/or shares referring to LEA (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram etc.). 10 per partner	230+/170
LEA Followers	LEA followers joined via website form (12 per partner)	283/204
Events	Stakeholder/dissemination events organised 2 per partner (min. of 10 persons attending)	11/34
Stakeholder database²	Identify at least 60 stakeholders per partner	543/1020
Publications	Distribute minimum 60 leaflets per partner	~800/1020
	2 articles published per partner (online AND/OR print) ³	10/34

Table 1: Summary of the LEA dissemination Google document.

***Note:** Not all numbers are yet completely accurate, as this document is a living document and partners are continuously adding information. Therefore, and as some reporting might be done with a delay by some partners, the provided numbers in this table can be considered as a general information about the level to which the individual tasks are completed; however, most tasks will actually have already achieved a higher number/result. These were the figures on 15th of February 2019.

² For information about the stakeholder database, please see Deliverable D6.2.

³ Updated details about the published articles can be found in the Google document at:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1jRqtUXGPvVqmMdUdi0eFqW9fkAfoVYizXWZDLLEyyc/edit#gid=0>

3. LEA dissemination channels

Several dissemination channels were established for the LEA project in order to reach a wide target audience including members of the general public. LEA uses a variety of different channels in order to be as versatile as possible. The individual channels will be discussed in more detail below.

OVERVIEW OF LEA DISSEMINATION CHANNELS

- **Online:** Website, blog, social media (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube), project newsletters, webinars
- **Face-to face:** events, workshops, conferences
- **Other:** Flyers, invitations, project materials, banners, t-shirts, mugs

Figure 2: Overview of LEA dissemination.

3.1. Project website: www.learntechaccelerator.eu

Having a working and well-maintained website is crucial when it comes to project dissemination. A website provides a place where all bits of information come together. The far-reaching success of LEA's dissemination can be seen by the satisfying numbers of page visits that the website has already received. After the first project year (and less than a year of the website being online), there have already been over 18.500 webpage visits (goal: 20.000 visits over the project run time) (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Webpage visits.

This is a remarkable result and shows the great impact the LEA project has already had and the wide interested it has created. Another good indicator for the successful dissemination work is the large number of project Followers that the project consortium has already attracted (current number: 283). More details about the website as well as the LEA Followers are discussed in Deliverables D6.1 and D2.3.

It has to be mentioned that the LEA website is a “work in progress”, as changes become necessary during the project lifetime due to developments in the project. Thus, the project website continues to improve and adapt to the most current project developments and pages might be added or deleted.

3.2. LEA news – blog and social stream

In addition to resources (such as project materials and public deliverables), webinars, general information about the project and a partners' area, the website also features a *news section*, which merges social media posts (on Facebook, Instagram and Twitter) and additionally offers a blog section. The LEA blog is essential, as it features only authentic and unique reports by members of the LEA consortium

and covers a variety of topics which are interesting to LEA stakeholders and Followers, such as conferences attended by the LEA team, the LEA school labs and reports of project activities. So far, 23 unique blog posts have been published on the LEA website with more to come.

Figure 4: LEA News and blog.

3.3. Webinars

The LEA webinars, which are usually held every two weeks, are a great tool to get information about the LEA project and related topics out into the public. The webinars are hosted on Adobe Connect (<https://connect.jyu.fi/lea>), can be attended for free and are available in the webinar section on the LEA project website under www.learnstechaccelerator.eu/webinars and on the LEA YouTube channel (www.youtube.com/channel/UCpqlRr9iLn1jBOPzZaGoZ33w) after they have initially aired. Table 2 below provides an overview of the webinars held so far.

As the LEA webinar series has shown to be well received by its audience, more webinars will be filmed and published over the coming months.

Nr.	Date	Topic	Experts
1	01 Sept. 2018	What is innovation procurement?	Ellinor Wallin & Kati Clements
2	03 Oct. 2018	Learntech 2018: AI, VR, robotics	Mikko Muilu & Jari Laru
3	17 Oct. 2018	Understanding the needs of the Demand: Municipalities & Schools	Isabel Capella Munar, Sonia Dominguez, Paula Huuska, Hanna Sahlberg
4	14 Nov. 2018	Suppliers' experience of PCP - Case Almerin	Teemu Laitinen
5	28 Nov. 2018	Professional competences required to utilize innovative technologies	Rita Freudenberg
6	12 Dec. 2018	Understanding the legal aspects of joined vs. coordinated innovation procurement	Marta Coto and Sara Bedin
7	09 Jan. 2019	Towards Easy Virtual Reality Content Creation	Jarmo Tanskanen / Visumo corporation
8	23 Jan. 2019	Special edition on LEA @BETT 2019	Kati Clements and Mikko Muilu are reporting from the BETT show
9	13 Feb. 2019	What is a Prior Information Notice?	Ellinor Wallin & Kati Clements
10	20 Feb. 2019	LEA school lab experiences	Rikard Ström, Isabella Calvagna, Paula Huuska, António Direito, Philipp Schüssler

Table 2: Schedule of LEA webinars in the first year.

WEBINAR 1: 19 SEPTEMBER 2018

Topic: **What is innovation procurement?**
 Experts: *Ellinor Wallin (EU Projekt Konsult) & Dr. Kati Clements*

WEBINAR 2: 03 OCTOBER 2018

Topic: **Learntech 2018: AI, VR, robotics**
 Experts: *Seinäjoki City Councillor Mikko Muilu & Oulu City Councillor Dr. Jari Laru*

WEBINAR 3: 17 OCTOBER 2018

Topic: **Understanding the needs of the Demand: Municipalities & Schools**
 Experts: *Isabel Capella Munar, Sonia Dominguez, Paula Huuska, Hanna Sahlberg*

WEBINAR 4: WEDNESDAY, 14 NOVEMBER 2018

Topic: **Suppliers' experience of PCP - Case Almeria**
 Expert: *Teemu Laitinen*

WEBINAR 5: WEDNESDAY, 28 NOVEMBER 2018

Topic: **Professional competences required to utilize innovative technologies**
 Expert: *Rita Freudenberg*

WEBINAR 6: WEDNESDAY, 12 DECEMBER 2018

Topic: **Understanding the legal aspects of joined vs. coordinated innovation procurement**
 Expert: *Marta Coto and Sara Bedin*

WEBINAR 7: WEDNESDAY, 09 JANUARY 2019

Topic: **Towards Easy Virtual Reality Content Creation**
 Experts: *Jarmo Tanskanen / Visumo corporation*

WEBINAR 8: LIVE FROM BETT - WED, 23 JAN. 2019

Topic: **Special edition on LEA @BETT 2019**
 Kati Clements and Mikko Muilu are reporting from the BETT show

Figure 5: LEA Webinars.

3.4. Social media

Social media is an essential tool for attracting a loyal “fan base”, which is why LEA is active on various social media channels. Altogether, the LEA social media platforms already have over 500 fans/followers (goal: 1.000 during the entire project run time).

LEA SOCIAL MEDIA

- **Facebook** : @LearntechAccelerator
- **Instagram**: @learntechaccelerator
- **Twitter**: @LEAaccelerator
- **LinkedIn**: www.linkedin.com/groups/6536874
- **YouTube**: www.youtube.com/channel/UCpqlRr9iLn1jBOpZaGoZ33w

Figure 6: LEA’s social media accounts.

Social media channel	Number of posts	Fans/followers/likes
Facebook	55	204
Instagram	33	58
Twitter	71	80
LinkedIn	3	155
YouTube	11	8

Table 3: LEA social media in numbers.

As Table 3 shows, LEA’s social media channels have been actively fed with content, which will continue to be done over the coming months. Additionally, partners have also been greatly involved in social media activities by posting and sharing LEA related content on their own channels/accounts. More social media activities are envisaged, with the goal of attracting even more social media followers and fans.

3.5. Newsletters

Two LEA newsletters have already been published, spreading information about LEA and the developments in the project. This is perfectly in line with the project goals, as a total of four newsletters is planned. Currently, LEA has 164 newsletter subscribers (goal: 200). As the newsletters are also available online and on social media, their actual reach is far greater. The published newsletters can be downloaded from the project website: www.learntechaccelerator.eu/resources

- **Newsletter #1: September 2018**
- **Newsletter #2: December 2018**
- **Newsletter #3: expected to be published in March 2019**
- **Newsletter #4: to be published later on during the project lifetime**

3.6. Events and conferences

The LEA consortium has participated in many events and conferences in order to promote the project. A detailed list of the conferences attended so far can be found in the annex to this document and in Deliverable D2.3. In addition to large events such as conferences, partners also host smaller, individual dissemination events to spread information about LEA and find new LEA Followers. In the first year, 11 such dissemination events were held by over half of the consortium members. This number will grow in the upcoming months, as more content is continuously created, which can be spread in these dissemination events. As several events attracted a much larger number of people than the required minimum of 10, the number of stakeholders present at dissemination events has already reached about 200 (goal: 200-500 stakeholders attending events). This number will rise, as more events are planned for the second project year.

Whether the events were big or small, the LEA consortium has been successfully working towards engaging event participants in the LEA project, mostly as new Followers. These face-to-face encounters proved to be a very successful means of raising awareness and attracting attention; therefore, a face-to-face strategy will continue to be followed in the second project year.

3.7. Materials

LEA materials are designed to raise interest in the project and to spread information about it. All partners have received the available project dissemination materials and are asked to continuously distribute them among their networks and at all dissemination opportunities they attend. The public project materials can be found at the project website and downloaded from: <https://www.learnstechaccelerator.eu/resources>

So far, the following materials have been produced:

Material	Description
Project flyer	General information about the project, benefits of LEA becoming a Follower, how to become a LEA Follower
Business card flyer	Ways to get in touch with LEA
Global edtech Think Tank invitation	Information & event invitation to the Think Tank, which took place during the London BETT show (January 2019)
LEA T-shirts (see figure 7)	All LEA consortium members received a LEA T-Shirt to be worn at events where LEA is present (such as the BETT show) in order to attract attention
LEA event roll-up (see figure 8)	The roll-up can be individualized for all partners and displayed at local events
LEA coffee mugs	LEA-branded mugs, handed out to all LEA partners

Table 4: List of LEA dissemination materials.

Figure 7: LEA T-shirts worn by the consortium members at the BETT Show 2019.

Figure 8: LEA Roll-up.

4. Recommendations

The LEA consortium has put much work into the dissemination of LEA in the first project year. In order to continue this process and to maintain LEA's reach and level of influence, the following activities and actions are recommended in terms of dissemination:

- **Continue to update the project website (news, adaptations, functionalities...)**
- **Present LEA at events such as conferences, shows, meetings, talks, which present an opportunity for dissemination**
- **Partner organisations have to involve their own networks**
- **Partners have to address people directly; face-to-face interaction is very successful**
- **Continue to be active on social media**
- **Continue to create project material (e.g. flyers, gadgets)**
- **Partners have to write news stories for the website's blog**
- **Partners have to continuously update the projects' Google document**
- **Inform procurers outside the partnership**
- **Contact companies interested in the LEA project**
- **Start disseminating the final project event in a timely manner**
- **Dissemination leader should send a weekly reminder for consortium members to carry out dissemination**

Figure 9: Recommendations for future dissemination in the LEA project.

5. Conclusion

In this document, the dissemination activities of the LEA project's first year are summarised. Dissemination is a vital part of project work, as it allows the project objectives and ideas to be more widely spread and to make them accessible to the stakeholders, target groups and the general public alike. LEA has had a systematic and effective dissemination approach.

It can be said that partners in the LEA project have been eagerly engaged in spreading the word about LEA, in order to get as many stakeholders involved as possible and to make the project seen and heard internationally. The project materials, including the website, have been well received. New materials will be added and existing dissemination tools will be fine-tuned. All LeA dissemination channels will continue to be filled with news and content relevant to the project.

ANNEX

List of conferences attended by the LEA consortium

Event	Location	Time
<i>Past events</i>		
ITK Days	Finland	April 2018
Swedish Edtech industry	Sweden	May 2018
EC-TEL	UK	September 2018
Dare to Learn	Finland	September 2018
Nordic Edtech Awards	Norway	September 2018
EcoProcura	The Netherlands	October 2018
European Week of Regions	Belgium	October 2019
Swedish Edtech	Sweden	October 2018
ICERI 2018	Spain	November 2018
Festival dell'Educazione	Italy	November 2018
Slush	Finland	December 2018
ICT 2018	Austria	December 2018
Online Educa	Germany	December 2018
BETT	UK	January 2019
Learning Technologies	UK	February 2019
<i>Future events</i>		
INTED 2019	Spain	March 2019
ITK päivät 2019	Finland	March 2019
<i>More events will be added</i>		

